

Press release | September 2023

The Engine for South European Deep Tech launches the second Open Call for the S3E Program

In its mission to accelerate entrepreneurship and innovation in Southern Europe, the EU-funded project S3E is launching the ultimate program of support for researchers, startups and corporates developing Deep Tech solutions with social and sustainable impact at their core.

The **S3E – Southern European Entrepreneurship Engine** consortium is pleased to announce the launch of its **second Open Call for the S3E program** — the EU-funded initiative fostering Deep Tech entrepreneurship in South European countries.

During the first iteration of the program, S3E successfully supported 14 research teams, 10 technology transfer offices, 12 deep tech startups and 10 matches between corporates and SMEs. Now the S3E program is coming back with a second edition to offer **new opportunities to the deep tech ecosystem** looking to bridge the go-to-market gap in Southern Europe.

"I totally recommend the S3E program to anyone who wants to turn their ideas into successful businesses. The program's effectiveness and the support we received were incredible, and it has given us the confidence to pursue our entrepreneurial dreams."

Alexandra Kortsinoglou, TriPHYTE Researcher
S3E Start, 2023 Cohort

What's the S3E Program and who is it for?

The S3E Accelerator Program is built around **3 tracks of bespoke services**, tailored to the needs of different groups operating within the deep tech innovation ecosystem.

- **S3E Start:** helps **research teams and tech transfer offices** to explore the commercial viability of their deep tech projects. Through an 18-week **online training program**, the selected research teams will learn first-hand about the processes required to develop a business case for science-based products or services. The teams will be paired with a mentor who will give them **1-1 support and mentorship** and will also have the opportunity to pitch in front of investors at the end of the program.

- **S3E Charge:** supports deep tech **startups in their growing phase** that want to improve their business model and learn how to access dilutive and non-dilutive funding. Over 14 weeks, the selected startups will receive **tailored mentorship** to guide them through the validation process of their product or service, and the creation of an investment-ready business plan. This track also includes **networking with leaders in entrepreneurship and innovation** and the opportunity to pitch in front of investors at the end of the program.
- **S3E Reverse:** connects corporate challenges with solutions developed by scaleups and SMEs thanks to our **Brokerage Program**, based on a successful open innovation methodology. To access this track, **large companies and public organisations** have to submit a deep tech challenge, acting as the 'Challengers'; in the second stage, **scaleups and SMEs** are invited to respond to the selected challenges with their innovative deep tech solutions or products, becoming the 'Solvers'. Participants from both sides will engage in a Brokerage program and receive expert support for business collaboration.

How to apply

The S3E Open Call #2 welcomes applications from the following countries:

- **South European countries:** Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia and Spain.
- **Associated countries:** Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia, Kosovo and Turkey.

Those interested in joining the S3E Program will need to apply via the designated online platform, making sure to answer all mandatory questions and selecting at least one of the UN Sustainable Development Goals their business or project is aligned with. The application form will be available on the [S3E website](#) from the opening day.

Timeline for S3E Open Call #2

- **18 September 2023 (12pm CET)** → The S3E Open call officially launches for the 3 tracks: S3E Start, S3E Charge and S3E Reverse
- **15 December 2023 (5pm CET)** → Deadline for applying to the S3E Charge (startups) and S3E Reverse (large organisations acting as 'Challengers')
- **12 January 2024 (5pm CET)** → Deadline for applying to S3E Start (research teams & tech transfer officers)

After receiving the applications and running an independent evaluation, the selected participants will be invited to join their respective track as part of the S3E Accelerator Program:

- **S3E Start** will be active from 6 February until 6 June 2024
- **S3E Charge** will run from 18 January until 26 April 2024
- **S3E Reverse** will develop its Brokerage Program between April and September 2024, after selecting the startup solvers to the challenges through the **Open Call for Solvers** that will be available from 15 January - 30 March 2024

S3E has already supported many successful deep tech projects, do not miss the chance to be part of the South European Deep Tech revolution!

More information about the project and the open call is available on the S3E [website](#) and social media channels.

S3E is an ambitious joint initiative launched in September 2022, funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe Programme. During its 30-month run, 4 partners from Portugal, Greece, Ireland and Spain have joined forces to make S3E a reality. The team includes experts from the research, innovation and acceleration ecosystem, together with policy and community building experts.

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